

Steering the world from where we are: An introduction to the sociocybernetics perspective

Patricia Eugenia Almaguer-Kalixto
Universidad de Zaragoza

Fabio Giglietto
University of Urbino 'Carlo Bo', Italy

Abstract

The concept of sociocybernetics has been shaped over the past 40 years at the intersection between first- and second-order cybernetics, constructive epistemology and systems science. This has produced a common language to bridge these different disciplines and a common basis for research analysing complex social problems. Sociocybernetics applies second-order cybernetics concepts to the study of societies, communities and groups in which first- and second-order reflexivity may play an important part, but it is not only a theoretical perspective in the abstract; it is also an approach that is applied to the analysis of cross-disciplinary issues such as systemic violence, the role of technology in society, environmental challenges, urban planning, community development, social identity and media representation, among many others. This article provides an introduction and a general conceptual description of second-order cybernetics in the broader context of cybernetics and systems sciences. It also presents the sociocybernetics debate as it stands today, after the 20-year anniversary of the Research Committee on Sociocybernetics' (RC51) activities within the International Sociological Association (ISA) and its contributions to understanding and acting upon an increasingly complex social world. Sociocybernetics is the science of turbulent societies that somehow continue to adapt themselves, despite the complexities they are confronted with. The articles in this monograph introduce some of the current work

of the research committee and showcase the extensive potential for sociocybernetics' interaction with other areas of sociology and contemporary debate.

Keywords

Complexity sciences, interdisciplinary, second-order cybernetics, sociocybernetics, systemic thinking

Introduction

The social systems identified in the last century have entered a stage of restructuring in which their fundamental elements (ideas, material forces and institutions) have undergone important changes. How is our discipline addressing the analysis of this transformation? In the words of Wallerstein, 'over the past two centuries, the dominant view in social science has been that the modern world shows a pattern of linear development in which all positive trends go upward in more or less linear fashion' (Wallerstein, 2015: 1). However, everything that we have taken for granted is changing, showing that far from equilibrium, we are experiencing irreversible social transformation that affects us at different scales.

We acknowledge that we have to elucidate it from different observation points, and here the sociocybernetics perspective is able to explain interconnections between emerging elements in a systemic way, recognizing the importance of the observer in the definition and analysis of the system and promoting second-order observation of the social systems that need improvement.

From a sociocybernetics perspective, an extensive analysis of the world system (Wallerstein, 1974, 2015; Wallerstein et al., 2013) has shown that 'the growing complexity of the world is most clearly visible on these large-scale levels, and effective steering is most urgently needed there to prevent further chaos or even continuing disaster' (Geyer, 2006: 24). The utopia of global democracy and neoliberalism which has been used to justify the process of globalization is taking paths other than those predicted by linear models: the idea of uninterrupted economic growth is giving way to evidence of exclusion and inequality, human migration seeking to leave misery behind in search of better living conditions, environmental crises and social discontent.

Systemic instability seems to indicate that the international system has been in a stage of structural change at least since the global economic crisis started in 2008 (Kotz, 2015). This is expressed in the strong rise of the extreme Right and extreme nationalism as a political force, and in parallel, in the crisis of legitimacy of democratic systems including terrorist attacks in the West, the aggravation of the war in Syria, stagnation and economic recession in emerging countries, the European Union crisis generated by the disastrous management of refugee flows and by Brexit, and Donald Trump's victory in the United States presidential elections. In this context of turbulent and uncertain scenarios, questions about the actors, factors and dynamics of change across the international system and their effects at other levels need to be raised (Sanahuja, 2017).

Are these isolated events, or are they evidence of a change of cycle within a complex system? We consider the latter, understanding that complex systems (García, 2006) are composed of interdependent subsystems with processes at different levels, linked to one another by structural relationships and maintaining a density of relationships both inside and outside the limits of the system. Other authors also note that contemporary social problems are also of growing complexity (La Porte, 1975; Maldonado, 2016) – that is to say their complexity is not static but it increases due their adaptation and capacity to ‘respond’ to the environment.

In this context of turbulent and uncertain scenarios, questions about the actors, factors and dynamics of change across the international system and their effects at other levels need to be raised. Sanahuja refers to profound changes in the economic and social structures and the patterns of power distribution on which the international system is based: governance crises, globalization without multilateralism, society’s questioning of the elites and the establishment, growing social gaps and states’ reduced capacity to meet them, the emergence of the extreme right as well as revisionist political discourse (Sanahuja, 2017).

From a systemic perspective we cannot understand the emergence of these changes without first understanding the environment of the system. The limitations and pressures of external elements generate changes that transform elements of the subsystems that form our society. The transformation of political elements that condition democratic systems and the negative radicalization of different factions that leads to violent demonstrations are irritations to the system that suggest structural change. The elements of international order that we knew – rules, entities, relationships – are brought into question. Faced with this process of restructuring, crisis and change, daily social life is made more complex by our instantaneous interactions, pouring out our emotions, desires and social expectations in message form, incessantly feeding the databases of social networks that are reconfiguring our ways of communicating, consuming and living.

Thus we want to address sociocybernetics as innovative sociological analysis that can contribute to our grasp of and approach to this era’s analytical challenges, acknowledging that innovation will come mainly via our capacity to articulate analytical proposals from other sociological perspectives or an interdisciplinary approach. This level of observation is based on the use of common language to ask new questions to current problems, providing a wider perspective on our social systems.

The realization of this monograph celebrates 20 years since the founding of the RC51 in 1998 but also, the first appearance of the concept of sociocybernetics in Felix Geyer and Johannes Hans Van der Zouwen’s edited volume containing a selection of papers presented at the 4th International Congress of Cybernetics and Systems in Amsterdam in August 1978. The authors, among them Niklas Luhmann, Herbert A Simon, Anatol Rapoport and Richard L Henshel, cover a wide variety of topics brought together by the conceptual framework of sociocybernetics.

Sociocybernetics addresses social complexity in a conceptual and methodological way, seeking to theorize beyond the old lineal, monocausal and multicausal scientific views via a more holistic approach including circular causality and emergence. What is the difference between sociocybernetics and other new systems theory approaches? Bailey (2006) emphasizes that sociocybernetics seeks to show how changes in systems

pre print version

come about. It analyses, among others, negative feedback that returns the system to the status quo, but most importantly it observes feedforward processes that enable steering, adaptation, change and movement.

Sociocybernetics focuses on the self-steering of social groups rather than deterministic control. Linkages exist not only among components of the observed system but also between the system and the observer, who is thus always part of the system. Methodologically speaking, sociocybernetics can be applied at the micro-level of interpersonal interaction, for instance at the level of family and small groups; at the meso-level, with groups of greater complexity such as institutional and organizational research, cultural and ethnic minorities, policy processes interactions; and at the macro-level with large societal units and their interactions (e.g. countries, international markets, international policy). The concept of steering implies observation. Indeed, second-order observation is one of the fundamental elements of this methodology: ‘the observation of the observation process and the reintroduction of information into the research system (feedback) becomes a permanent search and integration task’ (Marcuello, 2006: 10), independently of the scale of analysis. Birrer states that ‘the inclusion of the observer in the system brings into the spotlight the role of the observer, the effects the observer might produce in the system, and the responsibilities of an observer in that position’. This is one of the key aspects of sociocybernetics from which sociological frameworks can benefit (Birrer, 1999: 814).

Sociocybernetics’ roots and development: Standing on the shoulders of giants

This introduction to sociocybernetics does not include the history of its development. Several other works refer to the different stages and precursors of the complexity sciences, complex systems and sociocybernetics (Castellani and Hafferty, 2009; Giglietto, 2006; Maldonado, 2016; Ruiz-Ballesteros and Solana, 2013). In this *Current Sociology* monograph, Bernard Scott and Bernd Hornung refer to key authors who are mentioned briefly in this section.

Some authors refer to different generations of thought to address how the theory of information has been the root of the complex social systems theories. It is generally taken as a genesis or point of departure for theories of information and communication, on the one hand (Shannon and Weaver, 1949), and for Wiener’s (1948) theory of control and communication, on the other, which gave rise to a vast field of research that was given the name ‘cybernetics’. These two seminal works were generated in the context of the postwar period. They were part of an interdisciplinary intellectual movement that had an important impact on the study of circuits and control mechanisms of different types, fundamentally mechanical and biological but also psychological and social. Cybernetics highlighted the importance of feedback mechanisms and the information they provide in the processes of the organization and operation of certain systems. Another important point of departure is biology, with Ludwig von Bertalanffy’s *General System Theory* (1968).

pre print version

Although these works constitute the seed, Heinz von Foerster's (1960, 1984, 2003; Von Foerster et al., 1953) work on the cybernetics of cybernetics is at the root of socio-cybernetics development. Von Foerster, who also took part in the Macy Conferences on Cybernetics (1946–1953), proposes a distinction between cybernetics of the first and second order, the former concerning 'the study of observed systems' and the latter, 'the study of observation systems' (Von Foerster et al., 1953: 1). Its concerns include ethics, epistemology, self-referentiality and self-organizing capabilities of complex systems. In the social sciences, the systems perspective comes first through Parsons' (1951) *The Social System*. Parsons developed his ideas during a period when systems theory and cybernetics were becoming relevant to social and behavioural sciences (e.g. Buckley, 1967, 1993). Taking elements of these approaches, Parsons postulated that the systems treated by these sciences are open: that is, inserted into an environment with other systems. (Parsons, 1982).

Dialogue with other disciplines enabled the transfer of concepts seeking to explain social phenomena. Ilya Prigogine's *Introduction to Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes* (1961) deeply influenced the concept of social self-organization. His further work on non-equilibrium systems and complexity in the 1970s and 1980s were also regarded as key inputs to explain complex behaviour (Nicolis and Prigogine, 1989; Prigogine, 1980; Prigogine and Nicolis, 1977; Prigogine and Stengers, 1997). Anderson (1972), defining emerging complex phenomena where new properties appear at each level of complexity, was also key reading for systems scholars.

Niklas Luhmann (1982, 1992, 1995, 2012), originally strongly influenced by Parsons, and Edgar Morin (1977, 2001) popularized the notion of complexity in the social sciences during this period. Luhmann linked the notion of complexity with the ideas of relationship, possibility, contingency and probability, prioritizing relationships as constitutive elements of systems. He constructed his concept of social systems based on the concept of autopoiesis, which Maturana and Varela (1980, 1999) had developed from biology. The concept of adaptation is very important to understanding and explaining the evolution of social systems. Luhmann's first use of this term referred to it as a quality of systems to 'adapt to the environment and survive', clarifying that complex systems must also 'adapt to their own complexity' (1998: 53–54). The concept of adaptation was fundamental to later integrating Maturana and Varela's structural coupling with his explanation of societal systems (1980).

Other important references on the development of the sociocybernetics perspective include Buckley (1967, 1993) and Geyer and Van der Zouwen (1978, 1986, 2001). Walter Buckley and colleagues (1967, 1993) proposed a model of social systems based on general systems research, cybernetics and information and communication theory. They formulated a systemic perspective of society that includes the concepts of adaptability, morphogenesis, emergence and self-organization, which refer to the ability of systems to interact proactively (feedforward) against irritations in their environment. For Buckley, adaptation is an essential process in the system–environment relationship, while his concept of emergence is non-reductionist and includes downward causality between the internal emergent levels of a system.

Felix Geyer and Johannes Van der Zouwen took sociocybernetics to another level, stimulating a proliferation of debates, meetings and publications since the late 1970s.

pre print version

Together with other scholars, they analysed the core problems in social science caused by increasing societal complexity moving towards the proposition of a new methodology approach based on sociocybernetic principles. Geyer and Van der Zowen coordinated their Symposium and Section on Social Systems at the 4th International Congress of Cybernetics and Systems in Amsterdam in August 1978. A selection of those contributions was published in two volumes under the title *Sociocybernetics: An Actor-oriented Social Systems Approach*, whose discussion on the relevance of cybernetics and systems to a wide spectrum of social problems and its particular emphasis on methodology and the difficulties inherent in observing complex social systems are of particular value. The aspect of actor-orientation was later on developed in part by Tom Burns and his colleagues (1985), and Kjellman (2002).

The RC51 has been paramount in promoting this perspective. The group on sociocybernetics was founded in 1980 as an ad hoc ISA group within the framework of the meetings of the International Sociological Association. The group consolidated at these annual meetings in Mexico (1982), New Delhi (1986), Madrid (1990) and Bielefeld (1994). In Montreal (1998), the ISA recognized the group as the Research Committee on Sociocybernetics. Since then the group has met every year to develop academic debate and research discussion on a topic related to sociocybernetics.

Over the past 20 years, sociocybernetics has been discussed and developed in the context of the ISA, flourishing as it is applied to widely diverse subjects of study and applied research. The contents of RC51's *Journal of Sociocybernetics* (JoS) and of the papers and books produced by RC51 members give a good account of the variety of topics addressed and the different sociocybernetics approaches. The topics which have been discussed can also be explored in the proceedings of the 15 International Conferences on Sociocybernetics that have been organized up till now and in the proceedings of the ISA World Congresses of Sociology and the ISA Forums in which RC51 has participated since its foundation.

Sustainability is perhaps the theme most extensively explored in the JoS papers, from systems for social sustainability (Murray et al., 2007) to the analysis of space and time scales for modelling sustainable scenarios (Gallón, 2009). Menanteau-Horta (2012) analysed globalization and distorted development; other approaches include culture for sustainability (Larsson, 2012), the role of higher education in achieving sustainable development (Scott, 2009) and sustainable technological scenarios (Amemiya-Ramírez, 2014).

Methodological reflections have also proliferated in RC51 Sociocybernetics to propose going beyond the logic of the social sciences (Van Dijkum and Mens-Verhulst, 2002), from observing action in situ (Van Bockstaele et al., 2000), to participatory design (McIntyre, 2003) and community networks (Hofkirchner, 2009). Further innovative proposals include Ciberkultur@ as an interdisciplinary activity in research communities (Amozurrutia, 2009), SACS Toolkit (Castellani et al., 2009) and Raven and Gallón's Mapping (2010). A methodology to analyse policy processes as complex systems has been also proposed (Almaguer-Kalixto et al., 2014). Furthermore, these topics have been discussed in the JoS and in conferences.

Education too has been analysed from a sociocybernetics perspective, including the role of e-learning and the digital media environment (Tække and Paulsen, 2016). Other

pre print version

approaches, such as education and indigenous social movements (Flynn and Hay, 2000), a complex systems approach for action research in Mayan communities (Sidorova et al., 2013), and the evolution of communication media in Moche culture (Blanco, 2018) are recent developments in sociocybernetics. As the titles and authors suggest, sociocybernetics has moved from theoretical non-empirical analysis towards implementation in specific settings framing concrete social problems. The media and ICT have also been explored (Akahori, 2014; Vellar, 2009), as have environmental analysis (Connell, 2002–2003), political and historical analysis (Mezza-Garcia et al., 2014; Mitchell, 2016; Nicolopoulos, 2007; Scott, 2015), and lately the relationship between complexity and truth (Altmann and Peters, 2018).

Due to a strong interest in sociocybernetics in the Hispanic world there is a growing body of Spanish language literature in this field, thanks to those who have participated through RC51. In 1983, Parra-Luna already devoted an important part in his book *Elementos para una teoría formal del sistema social* to the discussion of sociocybernetics concepts. Marcuello (2006) has edited a body of work proposing the guidelines of the sociocybernetics approach with contributions from international key authors. The UNAM LabCOMplex group developed sociocybernetics in connection with the CiberCultur@ proposal (Amozurrutia, 2011, 2018; González, 2006; Maass et al., 2012). Lara-Rosano focuses on complex adaptive systems and their application to practical cases (Lara-Rosano, 2018), and Barrón's (2018) recent work on sociocybernetics and critical theory proposes a method that seeks to understand reproduction and steering of mediated communications.

Finally, two recent collective works with contributions from members of the RC51 research community are: *New Horizons for Second-order Cybernetics* (Riegler et al., 2017) and *Complexity Sciences: Theoretical and Empirical Approaches to Social Action* (Lisboa and Cerejo, 2018). Both publications reflect the present state of second-order cybernetics, sociocybernetics and their empirical implementation.

Perspectives on sociocybernetics theory and practice

This monograph consists of two parts. In the first article, 'The sociocybernetics of observation and reflexivity', Bernard Scott offers a very important argument about how sociocybernetics can clarify and bring order to two key social science concepts: observation and reflexivity. Scott provides an introduction to and conceptual overview of second-order cybernetics with a brief discussion of how this perspective differs from typical social science theorizing and what makes it useful for conceptual unification.

The article shows how in 1974 the distinction between first-order cybernetics, the cybernetics of observed systems, and second-order cybernetics (see Von Foerster, 2003) became of central importance in setting out the architecture of cybernetics as a transdiscipline and a metadiscipline, clearly positioning second-order cybernetics as relevant to the social sciences (psychology, anthropology, sociology) as a source of conceptual clarity and unification. Scott's article includes a treatment of Gordon Pask's cybernetic conversation theory (1961, 1976), which is particularly helpful as a conceptual framework for discussing observations and reflections in terms of the structure and dynamics of cognitive processes and interactions within and among collectivities. The relevance of

observation and reflexivity is paramount in social science theory, method and practice. Scott offers a useful discussion of how the concepts of observation, reflexivity and self-reference are used and debated in the social sciences. It sets out some of the theoretical and methodological implications of these propositions.

Bernd Hornung, in the second article, titled 'The challenges for sociocybernetics', explains the origin of sociocybernetics and its structuration in a normalized scientific community, in terms of Thomas S Kuhn (1996). Hornung offers a concise overview of sociocybernetics that is useful to a reader of general sociology without special knowledge in the field of sociocybernetics. He offers a journey from the early sociologists who worked within the frameworks of systems and cybernetics organizations through the central components of the theory, specific methods and applications.

Hornung also discusses the principal challenges for sociocybernetics today: on the one hand, the challenge of pulling together partial theories into an overarching theoretical framework indispensable for coping with contemporary large-scale and highly inter-related real-world problems; on the other, the challenge of remaining relevant and meaningful in the face of complex social problems with intricate connections between scales and social groups, problems such as social inequalities, different expression of violence, ecological threats, radicalism and misinformation, to mention just a few.

The third article, 'Models in sociocybernetics: A 20 year review at the ISA-RC51 on Sociocybernetics' by Luciano Gallón, is also theoretical, but moves into the methodological. Model construction is a specific method for information-processing and cognition and is the underlying philosophical epistemology of constructivism. It is not sociocybernetics' only method but it is one of its main approaches to systems analysis. Of course the term 'model' refers to an always incomplete and reduced representation. However, from the perspective of sociocybernetics it is a useful constructivist tool from which we can learn about complex problems, their components, functions and processes, and how to include the observer's point of view.

In his article Gallón poses the basic questions of those who venture into the field of sociocybernetics – What is a model? How do you know if a model is correct? Is the model useful? As he explains, second-order cybernetics, observation of the observer, is an integral approach to the core actions involved in constructing a model. The text draws on systems theory and reflects on the possibilities, alternatives, barriers and potentials involved in making models based on sociocybernetics. It is an inviting review of modeling theory.

The fourth article, 'Sociocybernetics and action research: Analysis and intervention in complex social problems', also addresses what sociocybernetics can contribute to methodological debates in sociology. The authors, Patricia E Almaguer-Kalixto, José A Amozurrutia and Margarita Maass, have been engaged in applied sociological analysis and intervention in different parts of Latin America and the Maghreb, developing methodological tools for a better analysis of emerging social action, using participatory action research (PAR) with local actors. From these interventions they have found that while PAR has proven a useful methodological framework, a better systematization of complex social research processes is required to make possible reflexivity at a participatory level and second-order observation of the full research system concerned.

pre print version

The article proposes a PAR model using conceptual and methodological elements of sociocybernetics, applying first- and second-order cybernetics and general systems theory to social sciences. The authors consider this model able to reinforce the systematization of PAR, enabling second-order reflexivity and a feedback process through information analysis and communication strategies. The first part of the article explains how concepts from sociocybernetics can contribute to this sociological methodology and discusses points of similarity between the two approaches and the basis of the model proposed. In the last part, the article addresses an empirical case of PAR developed in the context of the High Atlas in Morocco, using the model proposed. Making the case for sociocybernetics' contribution to PAR, the authors argue for the general value that sociocybernetics adds to social science, proposing that it can be helpful in analysing how social changes occur in complex settings.

While the first part of this monograph issue introduces the main conceptual tools traditionally ascribed to sociocybernetics, the second part illustrates how these tools can be applied to understanding and addressing specific issues in contemporary society. These range from better understanding of a media system after its profound digital transformation to the role of the media in a more inclusive society. The governance of collective recovery efforts after natural disasters, problems that arise in strongly polarized societies and the closely related problem of the spread of misinformation are also addressed.

Giovanni Boccia Artieri and Laura Gemini use Luhmann's social systems theory to describe the transformation of the contemporary media ecosystem. Their article, 'Mass media and the web in the light of Luhmann's media system', starts with a critique of the widely used paradigm that describes the system as 'a hybrid'. While hybridity underlines blurred/liquid boundaries (in this case between traditional and digital media), an approach informed by sociocybernetics relies on clear distinctions. From this perspective, to observe a system we need a boundary, which at the same time creates the system and its environment. This inherently ecological perspective allows the authors to discuss the different logics and the role of digital media – with specific reference to social media – within the mass media system.

Ubiquitous digital media have multiplied the number of opportunities to connect. Nevertheless, as Jesper Tække describes in his article, 'Acquisition of new communication media and social (dis)connectivity', it has also brought new forms of exclusion. Using the concept of *disconnectivity* and relying on both the work of media scholars and the framework provided by Luhmann's social systems theory, the author discusses the forms of social inclusion and exclusion introduced by different media throughout history, from writing to digital technology. From this perspective the networks formed by communications connected to other communications constitute the real social fabric of the society.

For this reason, it is crucial to understand the role digital media play in countering the disruptive effects of large-scale disasters. Starting with an analysis of recovery efforts following the two devastating earthquakes that affected the Japanese cities of Kobe in 1995 and Fukushima in 2011, Toru Takahashi's article describes the crucial decentralized approach made possible by what he calls 'societal media'. The article, titled 'Governing and societal media for building resilience: A sociocybernetic study of the disaster

recovery in Japan’, explains that coordinated grassroots efforts carried out by a multitude of actors (institutions, commercial and non-profit organizations) in the aftermath of both natural disasters relate directly to the core etymological roots of cybernetics (from the Greek word *kubernan*, ‘to steer’).

If large-scale natural disasters call for the coordination of multiple and diverse actors united by the common goal of aiding and supporting the victims and favouring the quickest possible recovery, steering becomes even more difficult in polarized and divided societies where conflict between actors seems to prevent any kind of collaboration. On 2 October 2016, Colombia went to the polls to ratify an agreement between the government and the FARC guerrillas, aimed at ending 50 years of armed conflict. Surprisingly, the proposal was rejected by a very small majority (50.22%) of the voters. Propelled by a sense of wonder at this, Michael Pateau’s article, ‘The Colombian peace process and the complexity of violence. A sociocybernetic observation’, leverages the vast literature on power, violence and memory through the lens of sociocybernetics to question the notion of the ‘culture of violence’ that often surfaces in debates about Colombian society. Pateau introduces and suggests instead the idea of a ‘system of violence’ surrounded by a cultural environment with its own historical memory deeply marked by the friend–enemy distinction (Schmitt, 1996).

Profoundly divided and polarized societies in which the friend–enemy distinction tends to prevail lack the minimal amount of common ground needed for proper democratic debate. For this reason it is important to pay attention to the processes that lead to such divisions. In their article, ‘“Fake news” is the invention of a liar: How false information circulates within the hybrid news system’, Fabio Giglietto, Laura Iannelli, Augusto Valeriani and Luca Rossi reconstruct the debate around fake news, pinpointing – following Von Foerster’s (2003) warning about the use of the word ‘truth’ – the inherently divisive meaning of the term. They suggest a radical change of perspective to second-order cybernetics that shifts the focus from the creator of false information to the perspectives, judgements and motivations of those exposed to such contents.

Sociocybernetics and the roots of the future

From Geyer’s (2006) perspective, the modern world is characterized by enormously synchronically and diachronically increased interdependence. Activities, decisions, processes are increasingly correlated in the present with more other activities, decisions and processes than used to be the case in the past. Being aware of this is what Norbert Elias called *Breitsicht* (broad-sight). At the same time, everything tends to have consequences that stretch ever longer into the future of what he called *Langsicht* (long-sight):

To be subjectively fully aware of the manifold facets of this interdependence explosion, which is boosted itself by the explosion of communications technologies, necessitates a considerable increase in both ‘*Breitsicht*’ and ‘*Langsicht*’ – in the world population at large, and particularly in its governing intellectual, financial, and industrial elites. Unfortunately, this awareness is often sorely lacking. The future of sociocybernetics (and of the world itself!) will largely depend on whether or not such an awareness of this increased interdependence – and especially

of its many essential consequences –will fully emerge, and will be applied to efforts to solve the world’s most outstanding steering problems. (Geyer, 2006: 25)¹

As the collection of papers presented in this monograph makes clear, the entire history of cybernetics and systems thinking is inextricably connected with the development of new technologies. It all began with a quantifiable measure of information, a simple communication system built around a sender, a receiver, a channel, and the theory of probability applied to address new issues, from improving transmissions to predicting the behaviour of particles and the trajectory of aircraft. Radar providing signals to guide ballistic tracking systems is used as a metaphor for studying feedback loops in humans and machines. The interdisciplinary efforts of scholars from different backgrounds, some united by the Macy Conferences, led to the proliferation of new ideas that influenced the development of artificial intelligence, computer science, public opinion polls, content analysis, human cognition and, of course, general theories about society. With this common background, approaching the study of society in terms of observing its systems, elements, networks of elements, boundaries and environments seems to work particularly well when it comes to understanding present times.

The more our digital interactions leave permanent traces, the easier it is to observe social systems. Ultimately, it also makes the behaviour of those social systems more unpredictable and harder to steer. The constant opportunity for real-time self-observation that the new digital technologies provide, enacts a process of reflexivity that can in turn lead to changes in our opinions and behaviours. As in classic feedback loops, these changes will in turn be observable and observed themselves, potentially leading to further change.

From this perspective, sociocybernetics is the science of turbulent societies that somehow continue to adapt themselves, despite the complexities they are confronted with. The contributions to this monograph present some of the current work of the research committee and showcase the extensive potential for sociocybernetics’ interaction with other areas of sociology and contemporary debate.

Funding

This research received partial support from Gobierno de Aragón and Fondos Feder “Construyendo Europa desde Aragón” 2014–2020, provided to GESES Research Group.

Note

1. Extract from the original manuscript. The text was published in Spanish in Geyer (2006).

ORCID iD’s

Patricia Eugenia Almaguer-Kalixto <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5944-7278>

Fabio Giglietto <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8019-1035>

References

- Akahori S (2014) The paradox of social ties after the ICT revolution: A second-order observation. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 12(1): 19–30.

pre print version

-
- Almaguer-Kalixto PE, Amozurrutia J and Marcuello C (2014) Analyzing policy processes as complex systems: The case of Mesoamerican sustainable development initiative. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 12(1/2): 31–52.
- Altmann P and Peters R (2018) Introduction: Special issue: Complexity and Truth. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 15(2): 1–4.
- Amemiya-Ramírez M (2014) Sustainable technology assessment and sustainable scenarios of techno social phenomena. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 12(1/2): 53–65.
- Amozurrutia JA (2009) Cibercultur@ as an interdisciplinary activity in research and local communities: Advances in an information / communication / knowledge computer system development. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 7(2): 73–88.
- Amozurrutia JA (2011) *Complejidad y ciencias sociales. Un modelo adaptativo para la investigación interdisciplinaria*. Ciudad de México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México.
- Amozurrutia JA (2018) A sociocybernetics approach to enhancing research reflexivity: An epistemological model for social analysis. In: Lisboa M and Cerejo D (eds) *Complexity Sciences: Theoretical and Empirical Approaches to Social Action*. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Anderson PW (1972) More is different. *Science* 177(4047): 393–396.
- Bailey K (2006) Sociocybernetics and social entropy theory. *Kybernetes* 35(3–4): 375–384.
- Barrón JC (2018) *Sociocibernética crítica: Un método geopolítico para el estudio estratégico del sistema de medios de comunicación no presencial en América del Norte*. Ciudad de México: CISAN–UNAM; Zaragoza: Universidad de Zaragoza.
- Birrer F (1999) Sustainability, democracy, and sociocybernetics. *Kybernetes* 28(6–7): 810–820.
- Blanco J (2018) The evolution of communication media in Moche culture. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 15(2): 100–121.
- Buckley W (1967) *Sociology and Modern Systems Theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Buckley W (1993) *La sociología y la teoría moderna de los sistemas*. Madrid: Amorrortu.
- Burns TR, Baumgartner T and Deville P (1985) *Man, Decisions, Society: The Theory of Actor–System Dynamics for Social Scientists*. New York, NY: Gordon & Breach.
- Castellani B and Hafferty F (2009) *Sociology and Complexity Science: A New Field of Inquiry*. Heidelberg: Springer.
- Castellani B, Hafferty F and Ball M (2009) E-social science from a systems perspective: Applying the SACS Toolkit. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 7(2): 89–106.
- Connell D (2002–2003) Multiple constructions of the environmental crisis: A sociocybernetic view. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 3(2): 1–12.
- Flynn D and Hay J (2000) Changing social focusing in Indigenous social movements. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 11(1): 3–24.
- Gallón L (2009) Space and time scales of human perspective and sustainability: Tools for modeling daily life dynamics. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 7(2): 34–46.
- García R (2006) *Sistemas complejos. Conceptos, método y fundamentación epistemológica de la investigación interdisciplinaria*. Barcelona: Editorial Gedisa.
- Geyer RF (2006) Reflexiones sobre el futuro de la sociocibernética. In: Marcuello C (ed.) *Sociocibernética, lineamientos de un paradigma*. Zaragoza: Institución ‘Fernando el Católico’.
- Geyer RF and Van der Zouwen J (eds) (1978) *Sociocybernetics: An Actor-oriented Social Systems Approach*, 2 vols. Boston, MA: Springer.
- Geyer RF and Van der Zouwen J (1986) *Sociocybernetics Paradoxes: Observation, Control and Evolution of Self-steering Systems*. London: SAGE.
- Geyer RF and Van der Zouwen J (2001) *Sociocybernetics: Complexity, Autopoiesis, and Observation of Social Systems*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press.

-
- Giglietto F (2006) *Alle radici del futuro: Dalla teoria dell'informazione ai sistemi sociali: una introduzione*. Milano: F. Angeli.
- González JA (2006) Sociocibernética y Cibercultur@: Perspectivas, promesas y retos de diálogos interdisciplinarios. In: Marcuello C (ed.) *Sociocibernética, lineamientos de un paradigma*. Zaragoza: Institución 'Fernando el Católico', pp. 407–448.
- Hofkirchner W (2009) 'Community' – where to from here? From 'networked individualism' towards 'community networks'. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 7(2): 62–72.
- Kjellman A (2002) The subject-oriented approach to knowledge and the role of Human consciousness. *International Review of Sociology* 12(2): 223–247.
- Kotz D (2015) *The Rise and Fall of Neoliberal Capitalism*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn TS (1996) *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- La Porte T (1975) *Organized Social Complexity: Challenge to Politics and Policy*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton Legacy Library.
- Lara-Rosano F (ed.) (2018) *Aplicaciones de las ciencias de la complejidad al diagnóstico e intervención en problemas sociales: Un enfoque transdisciplinario de aplicaciones de sistemas complejos adaptativos*. Ciudad de México: Editorial Colofón.
- Larsson N (2012) A survey of important decisions and settings needed for attaining a sustainable world. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 10(1/2): 71–80.
- Lisboa M and Cerejo D (eds) (2018) *Complexity Sciences: Theoretical and Empirical Approaches to Social Action*. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Luhmann N (1982) *The Differentiation of Society*. New York, NY: Columbia University Press.
- Luhmann N (1992) *Teoría de sistemas sociales*. Ciudad de México: Anthropos/UIA.
- Luhmann N (1995) *Social Systems*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Luhmann N (1998) *Sistemas sociales. Lineamientos para una teoría general*. Madrid: Anthropos.
- Luhmann N (2012) *Theory of Society*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Maass M, Amozurrutia JA, Almaguer-Kalixto P et al. (2012) *Sociocibernética, Cibercultur@ y sociedad*. Ciudad de México: CEIICH/UNAM.
- McIntyre J (2003) Participatory design: The Community of Practice (COP) approach and its relevance to strategic knowledge management and ethical governance. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 4(1): 1–22.
- Maldonado CE (2016) *Complejidad de las ciencias sociales y de otras ciencias y disciplinas*. Bogotá: Ediciones Desde Abajo.
- Marcuello C (ed.) (2006) *Sociocibernética, lineamientos de un paradigma*. Zaragoza: Institución 'Fernando el Católico'.
- Maturana HR and Varela FJ (1980) *Autopoiesis and Cognition: The Realization of the Living*. Dordrecht: Springer.
- Maturana H and Varela F (1999) *El árbol del conocimiento. Las bases biológicas del conocimiento humano*. Madrid: Debate.
- Menanteau-Horta D (2012) Globalization and distorted development: In search of a system perspective for sustainability. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 10(1): 25–43.
- Mezza-García N, Froese T and Fernández N (2014) Reflections on the complexity of ancient social heterarchies: Toward new models of social self-organization in pre-Hispanic Colombia. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 12(1): 3–17.
- Mitchell A (2016) Political legitimacy in Japan: A Luhmannian perspective. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 14(1): 15–27.
- Morin E (1977) *El Método, I: La naturaleza de la naturaleza*. Madrid: Cátedra.
- Morin E (2001) *El Método, V: La humanidad de la humanidad, la identidad humana*. Madrid: Cátedra.

pre print version

-
- Murray J, Dey C and Lenzen M (2007) Systems for social sustainability: Global connectedness and the Tabalu test. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 5(1–2): 34–56.
- Nicolis G and Prigogine I (1989) *Exploring Complexity: An Introduction*. New York: Freeman.
- Nicolopoulos P (2007) Systems theory, the western functional conception of development and the difference of value worlds and cultures. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 5(1/2): 57–67.
- Parra-Luna F (1983) *Elementos para una teoría formal del sistema social: una orientación crítica*. Madrid: Editorial Complutense.
- Parsons T (1951) *The Social System*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- Parsons T (1982) *On Institutions and Social Evolution*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Pask G (1961) *An Approach to Cybernetics*. London: Hutchinson.
- Pask G (1976) *Conversation Theory: Applications in Education and Epistemology*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Prigogine I (1961) *Introduction to Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes*, 2nd edn. New York, NY: Interscience.
- Prigogine I (1980) *From Being to Becoming*. New York, NY: Freeman.
- Prigogine I and Nicolis G (1977) *Self-organization in Non-equilibrium Systems*. New York, NY: Wiley-Interscience.
- Prigogine I and Stengers I (1997) *The End of Certainty: Time, Chaos, and the New Laws of Nature*. New York, NY: The Free Press.
- Raven J and Gallón L (2010) Conceptualising, mapping, and measuring social forces. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 8(1/2): 73–109.
- Riegler A, Müller KH and Umpleby SA (2017) *New Horizons for Second-order Cybernetics*. London: World Scientific.
- Ruiz-Ballesteros E and Solana JL (eds) (2013) *Complejidad y ciencias sociales*. Sevilla: Universidad Internacional de Andalucía.
- Sanahuja J (2017) Posglobalización y ascenso de la extrema derecha: Crisis de hegemonía y riesgos sistémicos en CEIPAZ. *Seguridad internacional y democracia: Guerras, militarización y fronteras Anuario 2016–2017*. Madrid: Centro de Educación e Investigación para la Paz.
- Schmitt C (1996) *The Concept of the Political*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Scott B (2009) The global conversation and the socio-biology of awareness and consciousness. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 7(2): 9–26.
- Scott B (2015) Minds in chains: A sociocybernetic analysis of the Abrahamic faiths. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 13(1): 1–17.
- Shannon CE and Weaver W (1949) *The Mathematical Theory of Communication*. Urbana: University of Illinois Press.
- Sidorova K, Quiroz Carranza R and Rivero Pérez AK (2013) Complex systems approach and critical thinking in the construction of the research project about the youth in a ‘marginalized’ community in Merida, Yucatan, Mexico. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 11(1/2): 25–45.
- Tække J and Paulsen ME (2016) Bildung in the era of digital media. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 14(1): 72–83.
- Van Bockstaele J, Van Bockstaele M and Godard-Plasman M (2000) Observing action in situ. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 1(2): 13–26.
- Van Dijkum C and Mens-Verhulst J (2002) Sociocybernetics: Going beyond the logic of the social sciences. *International Review of Sociology* 12(2): 193–200.
- Vellar A (2009) Shaping the pop: US TV series and Italian networked publics. *Journal of Sociocybernetics* 7(2): 144–160.
- Von Bertalanffy L (1968) *General System Theory: Foundations, Development, Applications*. New York, NY: George Braziller.

-
- Von Foerster H (1960) On self-organizing systems and their environments. In: Yovits M and Cameron S (eds) *Self-organizing Systems*. London: Pergamon Press, pp. 31–50.
- Von Foerster H (1984) *Observing Systems*. Seaside, CA: Intersystems Publications.
- Von Foerster H (2003) *Understanding Understanding: Essays on Cybernetics and Cognition*. New York, NY: Springer.
- Von Foerster H, Mead M and Teuber HL (1953) Editors' introduction. In: Von Foerster H, Mead M and Teuber HL (eds) *Cybernetics: Circular Causal and Feedback Mechanisms in Biological and Social Systems*. New York, NY: Josiah Macy Jr Foundation.
- Wallerstein I (1974) *The Modern World System, Capitalist Agriculture and the Origins of the European World Economy in the Sixteenth Century*. London: Academic Press.
- Wallerstein I (ed.) (2015) *The World is Out of Joint: World-historical Interpretations of Continuing Polarizations*. Boulder, CO: Paradigm Publishers.
- Wallerstein I, Lemert C and Aguirre-Rojas C (2013) *Uncertain Worlds: World-systems Analysis in Changing Times*. Boulder, CO: Paradigm Publishers.
- Wiener N (1948) *Cybernetics or Control and Communication in the animal and the Machine*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

pre print version